

**ANALOG TO DIGITAL CONVERTER
BY USING VCO AND SAMPLING
TECHNOLOGY**

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ABSTRACT [1]

Many voltages and currents in electronics vary continuously over some range of values. In digital circuitry the signal is at either one of two levels, representing the binary values of (1) and (0). An Analog-Digital Converter (ADC) obtains a digital value representing an input analog voltage. While a digital-analog converter (DAC) changes a digital value back in to an analog voltage. This novel approach enhances conversion accuracy and can be effectivity applied in modern communication systems.

Figure (1)

Analog and digital signals

Analog to digital conversion (A/D) is what we concern here and as there are many types of Analog to Digital converters we will present here in this research a new method of (A/D) and depending on VCO technology, by reading input voltage of the analog signal and this will give us a varying frequency output depending on the value of this analog input voltage and so by

translating this frequency into digits we will obtain a digital stream and so achieving an (A/D) device.

Analog to Digital Conversion [2]

Analog-to-Digital conversion is the process by which an analog quantity is converted to digital form. It is necessary when measured quantities must be in digital form for processing, display or storage purposes.

If we apply the analog signal to the VCO, concerning it as a control voltage finally we will get an oscillation with varying frequency related to the control varying voltage of the input signal.

In FM modulation we usually use VCO as a basic frequency modulator.

Figure (2)

VCO as FM modulator

The 555-timer Astable Multivibrator can be used as VCO to give a varying frequency output as concerning to the control input voltage.

Figure (3)

A VCO input and output streams

555 Timer Astable Multivibrator

The 555 timer is a versatile integrated circuit with many applications. The 555 is configured as an Astable or free-running Multivibrator, which is essentially a square-wave oscillator. The use of the 555 timers as a voltage-controlled oscillator (VCO) is discussed below.

555 Timer Operation as a Voltage-Controlled Oscillator (VCO)

A 555 timer can be set up to operate as a VCO by using the same external connections as for Astable operation, with the exception that a variable control voltage is applied to the CONT input (pin 5), as indicated in Figure (4)

Figure (4)

(The 555-timer connected as a voltage-controlled oscillator (VCO). Note the variable control voltage input on pin 5.)

As shown in Figure (4), the control voltage (V_{cont}) changes the threshold values of $\frac{1}{3}V_{CC}$ and $\frac{2}{3}V_{CC}$ for the internal comparators. With the control voltage, the upper value is V_{cont} and the lower value is $\frac{1}{2}V_{cont}$, as you can see by examining the internal diagram of the 555 timer (See Fig. 6). When the control voltage is varied, the output frequency also varies. An increase in V_{cont} increases the charging and

discharging time of the external capacitor and causes the frequency to decrease.

A decrease in V_{cont} decreases the charging and discharging time of the capacitor and causes the frequency to increase

Though by a varying input V_{cont} the output frequency will by relatively varies.

Figure (5)

(The VCO output frequency varies inversely with V_{cont} because the charging and discharging time of C_{ext} , is directly dependent on the control voltage).

Analog to Digital Converter using VCO technology

If we apply an analog signal to the control input of the 555 IC working as VCO we will get a varying frequency square wave output the rate of change in frequency depending on the value change in an input voltage at the control IC pin.

Figure (6)

Internal diagram of a 555 integrated circuit timer. (IC pin numbers are in parentheses.)

Let's take a practical example and see how we get the calculations:

for a certain design of the Astable Multivibrator and for a zero-control voltage an Astable Multivibrator will give an output signal as shown below:

Figure (7)

An Output of Astable Multivibrator

We can see obviously that there is a fixed high T_{HIGH} and low T_{LOW} time frequency of the output stream depending only on the design.

If we apply an analog signal to the control input, we will get:

Figure (8)

Output stream of VCO corresponding to analog input signal

We can see that input signal affect the period of T_{HIGH} , while T_{LOW} still fixed as it designed.

It's clearly obvious that, as a result of the input control voltage affecting the T_{HIGH} of the Astable Multivibrator output T_{HIGH} is directly corresponds to the input voltage value.

Now if we do sample the varying T_{HIGH} that depends on input V_{CONT} we will get a stream can be represented as a translation of the analog input signal value that applied to the V_{CONT} pin.

Figure (9)

Stream output as a translation of the input signal voltage.

**This sampling is done by a fixed frequency of sampling of time:
 T_s**

The number of samples per a period time is N_s and it is clearly a longer T_{HIGH} will result in a larger N_s for a fixed sampling frequency:

$$N_s \times T_{HIGH}$$

And as:

$$T_{HIGH} \propto V_{CONT}$$

$$T_{HIGH} = N_s T_s$$

Then:

$$V_{CONT} \propto N_s T_s$$

$$V_{CONT} = k N_s T_s \quad , k: \text{constant (v/sec)} \quad \dots\dots (1)$$

Conditions:

For the design of analog to digital converter frequency output Astable Multivibrator must be at least 10 times greater than frequency of analog input signal and the frequency of sampling must be at least 10 times greater than frequency of Astable Multivibrator, these conditions are necessary to reach a high accuracy of conversion.

The practical circuit (designed by Multisim 11) for an analog to digital converter is shown below:

figure (10)

(By Multisim.11) practical A/D circuit

This circuit is simply consisting of 4 stages:

A/D Circuit Block diagram

VCO circuit is simply as shown in the figure (10) consists of 555 as Astable Multivibrator and an analog input is applied to the control input.

The designed values of VCO parameters are as shown in figure (10).

The sampling circuit is consisted of two input AND gate with a very high frequency square wave as input 1 and the output of VCO is the input 2 of the AND gate.

The counter is counting the number of samples per period.

Memory is storing the result value of the counter at the end of a given period to be displayed through the seven segments output. This A/D works with range of maximum 20 kHz input frequency bandwidth of maximum input of 20 kHz and maximum peak voltage of $7v V_p$.

For an example input analog AM input of 5v 10kHz /100 Hz

We get these results:

Figure (11)

Multisin11. Practical A/D circuit output and input signal

The table below gives a comparison between input voltage (peak voltage) value of the input analog signal and the output Hex Code of the A/D output and these results are taken through the Multisim.11 practical circuit of our A/D:

Table 1:

Input voltage (v)	Output Hex Code
7.5	11H
8	0DH
10.5	11H
12	15H
12.5	18H
12.7	19H
12	15H
11.5	18H
10	19H
8	15H
7.5	10H
7	0FH
6.5	0CH
6	08H
4.5	09H
4	07H
4	06H
3.5	04H
3	03H
2.5	02H
2	00H

CONCLUSIONS:

This method is very useful to be used as a direct A/D converter and its accuracy comes from the way that voltage converted to time and time is a reflect to the voltage and though by fixed sampling frequency we can read that time to specify this voltage and this gives us a new method that can be used through this type of A/D as to be applied in communication circuits specially in the field of modulation and demodulation.

REFERENCES:

[1] ELECTRONIS DEVICES AND CIRCUIT THEORY

7TH EDITION, BY NASHELSKY AND BOYLESTAD

[2] ELECTRONIC DEVICES

7TH EDITION, BY Floyd